

The Problem of Identifying One's Identity and its Explosion in Indian English Literature

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Abstract

Why should we entail identity? Why should everyone run behind something and achieve greatness? It is all because they want to represent themselves as a superior identity. Hence character plays an essential role in our lives. Therefore what is a personality? It is like a name that everybody possesses on themselves. Some can explore it outwardly because they have given chances to do so. Some will fight for it because they are deprived of it due to so-called societal issues, and some exceptions are there that they don't even know what their identity is? In that case, some representation of them will show what their status is? Some people never allow fellow beings to blossom as an individual. They keep those buds under them and keep hiding their blooming. The victims of this identity crisis will mostly be women. Because they can ever be allowed by this patriarchy to expose what they are, and what they inherit within themselves. In this paper, I am going to flashlight upon the identity crisis of women in Indian society and Indian novels and to picture how some female characters in Indian books represent their identity.

Keywords:Identity, Social construction, Norms, Ideology, Intersectionality, Stereotypes, Prejudice, Bias, Sexism, Racism, Heterosexism, Classism, Ageism.

Understanding Identity

When does someone ask who you are? We will say our name. We think its identity. But that is not. Because the character is something that helps people to understand what we are; what we inherit. It can either be wealth or potentials of our knowledge. Depending on these credentials, people judge our identity. If you are sound in wealth, it doesn't require your identification. Your money will represent your identity. When you are not sound in wealth but talented, you will not be recognized in society because society gives priority to the paper of value but not to the proper human. Knowingly and unknowingly money pays a reasonable sum of dominance to others to recognize your identity. Some identity calamities evolve around the society since ages. That is nonentity but female identity. Are we sure that women are prearranged chances to explore their characters? By the way, I am not talking about the exceptional. I need to insist on the female subjugations and to broaden certain females who represent themselves exceptionally well in society by tearing their weird mask

of dependency. I want to let the fellow females like me who only speak through words in the paper but not articulating it orally, to understand their inner self and to make an emotional journey that dwells upon their identity.

Social Construction

Identity is a socially and historically constructed perception. We come to know about our status and the character of others through many mediums of dealings like family, friends, and relatives and the organization, peers, and the media. In spite of these many identity criteria, we still keep some deprivation in identifying others and force our discriminating dominance towards others in the name of sex, wealth, appearance, family background, social class, and age. There are still many issues therein, representing our identity to gain a socio-cultural status. Especially females in the society are facing gender bias that keeps them in the margin. There is a unique social construction of identity laid on females. They are: that they have to be someone's daughter, mother, and sister or whatever the roles they gain from the family and society. The name is given to her only for the convenience of others to call upon. The community has accustomed to this prior identity that only a male can go with his name that speaks everywhere about his particular personality. That is why Kamala Das speaks beautifully in her poem 'Spoiling the Name', "when you say, Don't spoil your name, I feel I must laugh, for I know I have a life, To be lived, and each nameless corpuscle in me, has its life to be lived..." In her case, the name is the identity that should be chosen by herself, not by anyone, and she has all her rights about her life and how to live on it. She doesn't like the identity name and adjusted it for thirty years already but not a minute once she decides that she doesn't want to live with it. So when someone states 'don't spoil your name,' she ridicules on it. There are certain characters who do not want to live with the coiled identity that has driven to her socially but want to enlarge their crushed status into a neatly ironed and straight one, I mean to say in terms neatly rolled that they gradually recover from their crushing nature and bring some straightened identity that shows who they really are.

Norms and Ideology

Where do we learn these ideologies and norms in establishing an identity, especially for a woman? It is not an emerging trend; it is an already existed crime that we do and internalize them in the course of our life. Everyone in society is bound to be a happy individual. But ideology we share with our peers, friends, and organization and even the Media framing certain norms to categorize the people with their identity. These values are significant because they generally come from places of supremacy, but also because we internalize them and take them for granted; they seem natural and the way things should be, and in turn, silhouette the way we see and understand the people, objects, practices, and institutions in our lives.

Our gender, race and civilization, sexual orientation, class, disability, religion, and age can play a considerable role in determining whether or not we have social, political, and monetary power. While many presume that anyone can accumulate social, economic and political power if they have talent, ability, and hard work, we also need to admit the way historically implanted prejudices are built into existing institutions and structures and consider how they create barriers and limit opportunities. But the prominent phenomena is one's self will never accept specific internalized identity instead will pose the society with their gigantic inner self at one point of their lives. Like the female characters in Indian English novels which have unveiled from their deficient socially constructed mask identity to articulating self.

Society has fixedly framed the blueprint of life for a woman much before she takes birth and fixed identities for her. It confines her survival through two-fold divisions between the

universal conception of men and women defining her as feminine as opposed to the masculine, the distinctiveness marked in the configuration of gender by society. Further, the connection of negativity with the features which fall into the pool of females, such as passivity, infantilism, emotionalism, and irrationality as opposed to adventure, determination, and rationality in male, considered positive virtues, do great harm to her self assessment and individual improvement. Moreover, the private sphere assigned to women in the patriarchal organism limits her role as a daughter, sister, wife, and mother and also facilitates the control of her body by the opposite sex. Within women themselves, divergence is established as a natural phenomenon.

Woman as a question with her own sets of emotions and desires at the conscious as well as the unconscious level remained less talked about, till the treatment of such issues by Anita Desai. In the identical year as the publication of the previously discussed novels in 1963, issued *Cry the Peacock* that brought out, with great sympathy and empathy, the hitherto unexplored space of female psyche- her annoyance, maladjustments and *Breaking the Stereotype* psychotic disorder which more advanced psychologists like Sigmund Freud had attributed to the organic determinism of women. In the novel, *Cry the Peacock*, Maya loses her reason at the disconnected and apathetic attitude of her husband. Driven to schizophrenia and the no acknowledgment of her unflinching and excessive love for life depicted through her intense emotional responses to the nature around her, she ends up killing her husband and taking away her own life.[5] In Indian society, where the marital world is the ultimate world promising happiness and succor for a conventional woman who has interiorized this kind of concept since her childhood, an atmosphere of separation and loneliness, can prove to be harmful not only for her but for other members as well. The examination of the dark and unknown recesses of the female self was a breakthrough in the realization of her prejudice and individuality destabilizing the societal expectations and stereotypes established on her status of otherness. In another novel titled *Fire on the Mountain* (1975) by Anita Desai which won her the Sahitya Academy Award, the author takes a peek into the psyche of her protagonist Nanda Kaul whose muteness at the face of her adulteress husband and the burden of looking after the great household teaming with children and grandchildren, finally goad her to search her own values away from the societal obligations as a wife, mother and a grandmother at the family house, Carginano, at Kasauli in Himachal Pradesh. However, Nanda Kaul's seclusion from the family does not make her droopy towards the rest of the society which is evident from her re-establishing the link with Raka, her granddaughter, who like her, a recluse and freedom-loving person, comes to live with her after the separation of her parents. Nanda is equally empathetic towards her old friend Ila Das, a social worker who often visits her and later on is raped and killed by the villagers for her intrusion in child marriage. The novel succeeds in smashing the stereotype of self sacrificing and self effacing woman, a mother and a wife in the character of Nanda Kaul in her refusal to carry with her the accounts of "too many servants, too many visitors... and too many children going to different schools and colleges at different times and too many tutors" [6] in search of her real self to the place of her new domicile. This real self of woman is not self-centered and isolated from society but the one that is well stuck in social certainty and has learned to care for itself. Long conserved notions of mother-daughter intimacy, adoration of woman's power of tolerance and her silence over private issues got dissolute in the fictional works which followed. Shashi Deshpande in her novel titled *The Dark Holds No Terror* makes her female protagonist Saru, a doctor by profession; share her mental agony for the sadistic sexual behavior of her husband, with her father as she comes to meet him after the death of her mother. Unlike the conventionally held image of the mother-daughter closeness, Saru's mother had never cherished her daughter and had never overlooked her for the childhood incident concerning the drowning of her younger brother in the village pond on the day she followed him. Saru comes back home to contract with the guilt, fear and emotional

confusion she has been undergoing as a daughter and the wife of a person called Manu, whose now brutish behavior during the nights that seems to be the projection of his restraint as a male at the greater social and trained placing of his wife, has left her complex and traumatic. Saru's physical coldness from her husband and sharing her anguish with her father at her parental home ease down her mental and emotional anxiety cleanses her vision and helps her emerge stronger and more confident to face life back home. The stereotype of the sexual frostiness in women has always been treated in ambiguous terms by society. The control over one's sexual desires and the averting of any overt display had been the hallmark features of an Indian woman. Poems have been written and sung in praise of women in literature and entertainment media to glorify such traits in them. However, ironically, sexual discretion on the part of a woman in a relationship with her husband offers enough bases for the justification of the male deviation on the ground of the wife's inability to please him. Indian literature in English has documented such false and unmerited images and sought to rectify them through the rendering of real women with real physical desires; she has every right to express and fulfill like any other free person. Shashi Deshpande takes up this issue in her novel *Roots and Shadows* where Indu, as she comes to her helping her right over the family house after the death of her great aunt Akka, contemplates over the futility of her married life with Jayant that has pounded her identity. It is at this point that she learns to claim the right over her body and her passions as she enters into a relationship with Naren, a distant relation. Even in the novel, *That Long Silence*, the interrogation of the preventive effect on marriage on women, is dealt with through the character of Jaya. The issue of rape within marriage destroying the old belief of the happy and peaceful marital continuation of our older generation crops up in the novel *The Binding Vine* where Urmi, the female lead comes transversely the letters of her dead mother -in-law only to reveal the dreadful and brutal nature of her marriage. Like these suppressed and suffocated women who have gone through many nuisances and I call them a menace to become out of this thwarted boundaries to achieve their selfhood. At last, it is their selfhood, which will help them to efface their filthy mask of dependency in the name of social norms to that of the male counterpart.

I, through this paper, insist every individual confront for their rights to gain their selfhood. Identity is the one which will elevate us as a persona in the world of drama. As Shakespeare proclaimed, the world is a stage, and we are the actors in it. Hence we have our roles to play on. We need not play the role of others. Let us stop dancing for other's tune. We are our composer, we are our director, and we are our destiny. Let us not include anyone to interfere and interpret our identity. Dear women and the marginal, please hold your head high, it is time for the identity world — no character then no independence. Alarm your heart and psyche that you are no more dependent and alert your identity you have to the new world to live on it. Never worry for the nostalgic nuisance of going behind the superior, a step ahead with your own identity that will bring you success at every step you take. Promote identity and perish dependence.

References

1. Anita Desai, *Fire on the Mountain* (England, Penguin, 1997) 30.
2. Kamala Das, *Spoiling the name*.
3. Shashi Deshpande's *That long silence*.
4. Shashi Deshpande's *The Binding Vine*.
5. Shashi Deshpande's *Dark Holds No Terror*.